

UDC 640.412:338.46]:616-036.21
DOI: 10.31866/2616-7468.3.2.2020.219691

**SCIENTIFIC
SUBSTANTIATION
OF THE HOTEL BUSINESS
COMPLIANCE
IN APANDEMIC
CONDITIONS**

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The topicality. The conditions of the pandemic lockdown prompted economic entities to restructure their activities in accordance with the new communication and operational rules. The service sector, the main purpose of which is the leisure organization, it has suffered the most from quarantine, as it has been banned. Therefore, some institutions have closed down, unable to withstand the crisis tendencies in the consumer market, financial pressure from landlords, and some have reformatted the business to new conditions of interaction with customers – remote services and delivery.

Mitigation of quarantine has helped revive activities, but it is legitimate within the protocols and regulations of local and state authorities to prevent the spread of viral infections. Therefore, the management of economic entities implements compliance control, the purpose of which is to carry out economic activities in accordance with laws, regulations and protocols, deviation or ignoring which creates risks of reputational and financial losses. Compliance control identifies economic and reputational risks, carries out prevention and management, forming a set of real measures to protect business and its owners. Thus, the implementation of a compliance control system is an important component of the development strategy of economic entities, including the hotel business, and a relevant object of study.

Purpose and methods. The purpose of the study is to theoretically analyze the compliance of hotel services and the formation of a model that identifies areas for improvement of hotel services in pandemic risks. The comparative nature of compliance as a category of proof of compliance with certain limitations contributed to the use in the research process of a set of general scientific methods, such as abstraction, analysis and synthesis, modeling, elimination of factors influencing the object of study, gap method for scoring compliance and allowed to substantiate the proposed imperatives of the framework conditions of compliance in the hotel business. **Results.** An empirical assessment of the financial losses of hotels from the pandemic caused by COVID-19 has been carried through in Ukraine. The directions of compliance of hotel service have been formed. The imperatives of framework conditions of service in hotels in the conditions

of the COVID-19 pandemic have been compiled. The compliance of hotel service compliance has been screened by the gap method. **Conclusions and discussions.** It is scientifically substantiated that the conceptualization of compliance control of hotel services is an urgent scientific task, as it allows to study the requirements for it and to comply with what is necessary in quarantine conditions. Further research needs to be deepened in order to assess the financial gaps in the implementation of the imperatives of the framework conditions in the business processes of the hotel, as well as to assess new forms of hotel services that have emerged in the world hotel business during the pandemic.

Keywords: compliance control, hotel service, COVID-19, gap method.

The topicality of the problem

Formulation of the problem. Modern business society is experiencing a pandemic crisis, which caused a “plateau” effect and forced service companies to reconsider the standards of management and service, regulated rules and activity principles. In this regard, the new conditions and requirements for hotel services require the improvement of business processes and the construction of a compliance system – internal policies and procedures based on regulations, including sanitary and epidemiological guidelines. First of all, the service processes underwent reformatting the staff must work according to the algorithm of health and safety: temperature screening; preventive disinfection of workplaces, surfaces, floors; ethics of communication; features of food organization, etc. Moreover, compliance control (compliance control) in the hotel is carried out both by internal sources (management, business owners and franchisors) and external (government regulators, customers, and partners).

State study of the problem. In the scientific literature, the definition of compliance and the development of its basic concepts have been worked out in many areas, including hotel. Thus, Rafael Robina-Ramírez, M. Isabel Sanchez-Hernandez, Carlos Diaz-Caro (Robina-Ramírez et al., 2020) studied the compliance of corporate protocols of hotels of different categories to the Spain legislation; Vovk O., Kovalchuk A., Pasiychuk A. (2020) argued the need for a compliance approach to enterprise management; Pererva P. (2017) is the creation of an appropriate unit that correlates with corporate strategy.

However, the global pandemic caused by the spread of the SARS-CoV-2 virus (known as the COVID-19 virus) has made significant adjustments to hotel operations, necessitating innovative approaches to business processes and hotel services.

Given the above, the works of Grishina O. (2020), who studied the problems of the operation of quarantined hotels, are relevant in the formation of the patchwork of current innovations in hotel services; Rolska R., Sharan L. and others (2019), who studied the introduction of specialized packages with rehabilitation services in a family-type hotel; Pozdnyakova O. (2019), where the practice of educational and rehabilitation institutions is considered; Sidoruk S., Polishchuk L., Tyschuk I. (2019), who focused on the organization of SMART-hotels as a direction of reformatting the service in order to minimize the risks of infection, etc.

The authors of the above research have identified problems in the operation of hotels, the formation of an effective service system in a viral pandemic, which have become objects of compliance in our study.

Compliance affectometry, in turn, requires an appropriate methodology for processing, which will provide a reliable and timely assessment of the results of research and implementation of organizational and managerial measures of hotel services in pandemic risks. Studying scientific experience in various fields of activity, in particular risk assessment, it seems most interesting in this context to apply the gap method. It is used in the assessment of interest rate risks of the bank (Buchko, 2014), cybersecurity analysis (Ilyashenko et al., 2018), assessment of anti-corruption compliance (Okunev et al., 2018). Attempts to apply the gap method in tourism can be traced in the works of Saukh I. (2017) as a means of decision-making in the formation of a strategy for the financial potential development of the tourism enterprise; Baumgarten I. V. (2017) is as a tool for management analysis of the hotel business; Chan I. (Chan, 2004) is as a study of gaps in the perception of hotel marketing and information technology support for business tourists.

Unresolved issues. The topicality of the study is to determine the areas of compliance of hotel services in quarantine and post-quarantine conditions caused by pandemic risks, and their assessment using the gap method.

Purpose and research methods

The purpose of the article is a theoretical analysis of compliance with hotel services and identifies areas for improvement of hotel service standards in pandemic risks.

Research methods. The comparative nature of compliance as a category of proof of compliance with certain restrictions contributed to the use of general scientific methods of the hotel service complex research: abstraction, analysis and synthesis, modeling, elimination, which ensured the systematic nature of the study of compliance imperatives and the definition of its directions in the hotel business.

The information base of the study was the scientific works of domestic and foreign scientists, their achievements in the application of compliance and gap analysis in various fields, including the hotel business.

The object of the study is the compliance control of hotel services.

The subject of the research is service process and facilities that form the molecular model of the hotel business in a pandemic.

Scientific novelty is to determine the patterns of compliance control in the hotel business in a viral lockdown, which will ensure the effective functioning of the enterprise through the provision of hotel services in accordance with modern requirements and sanitary and hygienic standards.

Research results

Economic entities today operate in difficult pandemic conditions that have affected the development of global and regional markets caused a crisis in the domestic hotel business in particular. The scientific and business community is concerned about the risks of outbreaks of infection of employees and tourists in hotels, which are likely due to non-sanitary non-compliance of hotels with modern requirements, which may eventually lead to the cessation of these enterprises as business entities. The blocking of tourist flows from all sources, including domestic ones, has caused the shutdown of many hotel enterprises, in particular in the segment of luxury, small hotel business, and

medical and health accommodation facilities. Those who continued to work faced the problem of ultra-low workload. Color delineation of geolocations by levels of infection risks makes adjustments to quarantine requirements and permits for certain hotel services. However, this means extending the period of unprofitable hotels.

In order to assess the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the hotel business in Ukraine, experts from Vertex Hotel Group and Colliers International (Ukraine) conducted a study of the hotel real estate market in Ukraine, during which it was found that 85% of respondent hotels and inform about the risk of bankruptcy, or prepare for closure (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. The state of hotel entities functioning during the quarantine caused by the epidemic COVID-19, % of respondents
 Source: Colliers International (Ukraine), 2020

The pandemic crisis has caused significant economic losses to the hotel business. Taking into account the data received from Colliers International (Ukraine) and Vertex Hotel Group for one month of quarantine, we eliminate the indicators to the duration of the restrictions predicted by experts – October 2020 (8 months) (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Empirical assessment of the amount of financial losses of hotel entities during quarantine caused by the epidemic COVID-19,% of respondents
 Source: compiled by the author for Colliers International (Ukraine), 2020

Figure 2 shows the depression in the hotel sector of high-end hotels, while the losses of low and medium price categories are much lower, because they have a smaller number of rooms and a reduced range of additional services. In these conditions, the resumption of activities is possible only at a slow pace as tourist demand intensifies, along with the reformatting of hotel services, the introduction of new approaches to creating safe working conditions and consumption of hospitality services.

New market challenges, a protracted quarantine period and the growing urgency of finding ways to survive are leading to a unique pandemic crisis. In these new conditions for hotel operators, innovative strategic pathways must combine compliance with the comfort of hotel service and pandemic protocols and requirements. In our opinion, it is expedient in this situation to use paired molecular docking and to determine the most advantageous architecture of some business processes (molecules) relative to others. The main purpose of docking is to obtain optimal (according to the established criteria) spatial structures in the organization of hotel services (Meng and others, 2004). That is, the result is molecular modeling – a purposeful modification of the structure of molecules in a dynamic model in order to establish the dependencies of the type structure-property (Opeid & Schweik, 2008). In our study, the application of this methodology is caused by the need to study the internal organization and service relationships of “molecules” components of the guest cycle to identify opportunities for their modification under the influence of new protocols of behavior and compliance with them. When building a molecular model of compliance with hotel services, we will be guided by the principle: compliance with hotel service is fixed, and the requirements for the organization of health processes unfold around it in various ways: optimal and maximum tools and procedures. The first involves the use of personal protective equipment (masks, rubber gloves), constant temperature screening of staff and guests, hourly hygienic cleaning and disinfection of surfaces, the presence of disinfectants in all public places. The second are significant equipment costs: frames-sanitizers, medical boxes, machines with masks and rubber gloves.

Thus, the system of compliance with hotel services includes objects and processes, which will be shown schematically, based on conceptual hotel services: accommodation, food, additional household and business services, sports and recreational services (Fig. 3).

Creating conditions of individual isolation at the first symptoms of the disease, providing rehabilitation services for people who have contracted a viral disease, become an important component of complementary hotel services in conditions of pandemic risks, so their implementation is important for the functioning of the accommodation.

This approach to the compliance of hotel services allowed compiling the imperatives of the framework conditions of service in hotels in a pandemic COVID-19 (Table 1).

Today, all accommodation facilities in Ukraine are recommended to be guided by Part 1 of Art. 68 (Medical and sanitary provision of recreation) as amended in accordance with the Law № 5460-VI of 16.10.2012 (Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, 2012), according to which the owners and managers of accommodation are obliged to create healthy and safe conditions, to provide the possibility to provide the necessary medical care to the persons having a rest. Although guests are probably already familiar with the rules of conduct and measures to reduce the risk of viral infection, they should be reminded on the official website of the hotel, where the guest can read the information when booking services; in the mobile application that he will use while at the hotel; in printed materials (booklets, memos, etc.) that can be placed at the reception desk, in

rooms, places of recreational recreation, trade halls of food establishments. In addition, social distancing measures, together with systematic hand hygiene and respiratory etiquette, are essential to prevent the transmission of COVID-19. Thus, the safety of guests and employees in hotels is the direct responsibility of business organizers as participants in the global process of stopping the pandemic and preventing the risks of a new wave of viral infections in the company and beyond.

Fig. 3. Objects and processes of compliance control of hotel service
 Source: compiled by the authors

Table. 1. Imperatives of framework conditions of service in hotels in the conditions of pandemic COVID-19

Rules	Procedures	Means	Operating activities
The service process “Incoming guest”			
Ensuring the sanitary and epidemiological safety of guests and staff	Systematic temperature screening of staff and guests Safe distance in communications Transparent protective screens on reception desks, concierges Hourly treatment of contact surfaces and floors of the reception area Disinfection of upholstered furniture with steam generators at least every 2-3 hours Interval air conditioning with the addition of disinfectants	- marking a safe distance on the floor - medical masks - rubber gloves - frames- sanitizers - hand sanitizers - infrared contactless thermometers - medical kit - special containers for used personal protective equipment	Training of personnel in the rules of work in the conditions of risks of spreading epidemiological diseases Upon check-in, the guest must indicate whether he / she has been in contact with patients with COVID-19 during the last 14 days. Providing guests with suspected viral infection with places for observation with full hotel service
Service process “Floor service”			
Ensuring the sanitary and epidemiological safety of guests and staff Prevention of infection risk	Maintaining security in the communications of guests on the floor Daily routine cleaning with sanitation of the surfaces and floors of the area in the rooms Air conditioning of the room with the addition of disinfectants during cleaning	- markings of safe distance on the floor in the corridors - boxing with medical masks, rubber gloves - hand sanitizers in the rooms and on the floor - airtight packaging of items in the rooms	Accommodation for no more than one guest in the room, except for couples and other relatives who permanently live together Daily monitoring of the health of guests and staff Providing guarantees of care for the safety of services provided and prevention of infection
Business process “Food organization”			
Ensuring adequate nutrition in compliance with the sanitary and epidemiological safety of the guest and staff	Keeping a safe distance in communications Hourly treatment of surfaces and floors of the shopping area Interval air conditioning with the addition of disinfectants Control over the safe number of visitors	- marking a safe distance on the floor - medical masks - hand sanitizers - packing food in a safe closed container - organization of room service	Training of personnel in the rules of work in the conditions of risks of spreading epidemiological diseases Prevent the risk of infecting the guest and staff Providing room service to guests with

Rules	Procedures	Means	Operating activities
			a suspected viral infection
Сервісні процеси «Організація бізнес-послуг»			
Prevention of infectious and viral diseases Ensuring the sanitary and epidemiological safety of guests and staff	Hourly treatment of surfaces and floors of the shopping area Interval air conditioning with the addition of disinfectants Control over the safe number of visitors	- marking a safe distance on the floor - medical masks - rubber gloves - hand sanitizers - infrared contactless thermometers - special containers for used personal protective equipment - airtight packaging of individual stationery	Training of personnel in the rules of work in the conditions of risks of spreading epidemiological diseases Ensuring social distance Contact management
Service processes “Creation of conditions of individual isolation at the first symptoms of a disease”			
Relieving the risk of infection Prevention of the spread of coronavirus infection COVID-19 and other viruses and strains	Isolation of a guest in the room temporarily before the intervention of local health authorities and provided that the room is not provided to other guests Cleaning and disinfection of the room where the sick person is	- boxing with medical masks, rubber gloves - hand sanitizers in the room and on the floor - airtight packaging of items of use	Providing conditions for self-isolation

Source: compiled by the authors according to the Resolution of the Ministry of Health № 32 (Ministry of Health, 2020a); Resolution of the Ministry of Health № 36 (Ministry of Health, 2020b); Operational considerations...(World Health Organization, 2020)

This provides grounds for assessing the level of implementation of the above recommendations, the readiness of hotels to implement and comply with the framework conditions of service in epidemiological conditions. The chosen method of gap analysis (from the English Gap – gap, imbalance) involves determining the gap indicator, which is relevant to use as a sensitive indicator of the company’s response to changes in operating conditions, including hotel services (Chan, 2004). This justifies the formation of current innovations in hotel services and their compliance with the framework conditions of the epidemiological situation. Based on the proposed molecular model and certain imperatives, we analyze the current state of hotel services in Ukraine by gap (deviation of the expected from the real state), where the main criterion is the sanitary and hygienic requirements for customer and internal relations. The evaluation

was carried out according to a 5-point system, where “0” is a lack of appropriate tools and procedures; “5” is their full application and compliance (Table 2).

Table 2. Scoring of compliance of hotel service by a gap method

Basic components	Reality			Expectation			Gap		
	4-	3*	2* and without category	4-	3*	2* and without category	4-	3*	2* and without category
Accommodation	4	3,5	1	5	3	2	-1	0,5	-1
Food	4,5	3	1	5	3	2	-0,5	0	1
Business services	4,5	2,5	0,5	5	3	1	-0,5	-0,5	-0,5
Health care	3,5	2	2	5	4	1	-1,5	-2	-1
Cumulative gap	-	-	-	-	-	-	-3,5	-2	-1,5

Source: compiled by the authors based on the results of the evaluation of feedback on the platform <https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1tFEefaZ8Fyos6A9vc1ZD6oZk82s3iGS-261xYEXYEO/edit?usp=sharing>

The findings show negative results between the expected and actual state of health compliance. Own research has shown almost complete disregard of quarantine requirements by hotels in most seaside resorts, due to local apathy. At the same time, the capital’s hotels are also in no hurry to implement total health compliance, hoping for a quick repayment of the epidemic. Thus, the vast majority of hotels use the optimal configuration of the molecular model of hotel services. According to the results of table 3, we form a projection of the visual reflection on the graph (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Map of positioning the gap on the basic components of hotel services in a pandemic conditions
 Source: compiled by the authors

It is obvious that the most distant from the standard were high-class hotels, for which medical care is a mandatory component of services. This can be explained by the collinearity of health requirements and ensuring a high level of comfort. Other categories of hotels are more flexible in this regard and seek to increase their presence in the market of hotel services, taking advantage of the situation. It is projected that all hotels focused on food services, provided food delivery to the room, showing the approach of the vectors to the standard (where all the values of gaps are equal to 1). Ironically, the least attention is paid to medical care, which is reduced to the formalities of temperature screening and first aid, ambulance call.

Characterizing the cumulative gap, we see negative values for all categories of hotels. The negative gap diagnoses a situation where expectations (expected obligations hotel) exceed reality (given the possibility of hotel service). Such estimates determine the need for operational and strategic management of gaps, which is that the size and type of gap should be consistent with the forecasts and trends of the pandemic situation in Ukraine and the world. Such estimates determine the need for operational and strategic management of gaps, which is that the size and type of gap should be consistent with the forecasts and trends of the pandemic situation in Ukraine and the world.

Negative gap, for its part, predicts the risk of financial losses due to penalties and reduced customer focus. Thus, it is important for the hotel management that the gap corresponds to the direction of movement of positive impressions of guests, which absorbs loyalty and increase profits. That is, it was positive or at least zero. Thus, the gap, in this case, is considered as a measure of reputational risk to which the hotel is exposed in a fixed timeframe fixed by certain criteria (crisis cycle, season, etc.).

Compliance control, thus, will consist in the formation and observance of hotel service standards that comply with organizational procedures and health protocols in conditions of risk of infection. Of course, the additional costs are quite significant in aggregation, but prevent penalties and complaints that can lead to closure and downtime of the hotel.

Thus, hotels should be armed with at least a minimum set of rules, procedures and means of health care and exercise internal and external compliance control over their implementation.

Conclusions and discussion of results

Assessment of the state of functioning and financial losses of hotel entities in the COVID-19 pandemic allows us to note that the conceptualization of compliance control in the hotel business is especially relevant with quarantine requirements, as it allows studying and scientifically justifying directions of hotel service compliance. Elaboration of framework conditions as imperatives of activity in modern conditions is strategically important for hotel management, in particular as a tool of competitiveness.

Based on the study, some conclusions can be drawn about the compliance of hotel services in the context of pandemic risks:

- difficult conditions caused by the COVID-19 pandemic led to the complete closure or suspension of hotels in Ukraine, and only a small number of companies entered the struggle for survival;

– inevitable changes in the conduct of economic activity in the new conditions, the service system encourage participants in the hotel services market to seek unique strategies and tactics;

– hotel service is considered as the interaction of objects and processes that are compliant and require additional standardization, taking into account legislation aimed at preventing a viral pandemic;

– service reactivation strategy, which involves the introduction of a certain configuration of the molecular model of hotel services, can be the key to a successful exit of hotels from the pandemic crisis;

– studies of the level of hotels' responsibility for creating safe conditions for guests and staff using the gap method suggest that there is an insufficient level of sanitary and epidemiological safety in hotels, which, in turn, will reduce the contingent and financial losses.

The introduction of rules, procedures and means to prevent infection is projected to become a new etiquette of relations, part of corporate culture. Health and safety requirements will gradually diffuse; natural symbiosis will ensure the comfort and safety of customers and hotel staff, thereby increasing its reputation capital.

During the collection and processing of the research material, the main problems and limitations related to access to protocols and procedures for health care of hotels were outlined, so most of the conclusions are hypothetical. In addition, the public platform survey lacks subjectivity and a wide range of hotels by category and destination, making it difficult to assess survey results. Further research requires the elimination of subjectivity in feedback by professional sampling. It is promising to deepen the assessment of financial gaps in the implementation of the imperatives of the framework conditions in the business processes of the hotel, as well as the evaluation of new forms of hotel services that have emerged in the world practice of hotel business during the pandemic.

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The article was received on August 17, 2020

УДК 640.412:338.46]:616-036.21

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НАУКОВЕ ОБГРУНТУВАННЯ КОМПЛАЄНСА ГОТЕЛЬНОГО БІЗНЕСУ В УМОВАХ ПАНДЕМІЇ

Актуальність. Умови пандемічного локдауну спонукали економічні суб'єкти перебувати діяльність відповідно до нових комунікативних та операційних правил. Сфера послуг, основною метою якої є організація дозвілля, найбільше постраждала від карантину, адже опинилась під забороною. Тому частина закладів згорнула діяльність, не витримавши кризових тенденцій на споживчому ринку, фінансового тиску з боку орендодавців, а частина переформатувала бізнес на нові умови взаємодії з клієнтами – дистанційні сервіси і доставки.

Пом'якшення карантину сприяло поживленню діяльності, проте вона легітимна в межах протоколів та нормативних актів місцевих та державних органів влади щодо профілактики поширення вірусного зараження. Тому менеджмент економічних суб'єктів впроваджує комплаєнс-контроль, метою якого є здійснення господарської діяльності у відповідності із законодавчими, нормативними актами та протоколами, відхилення або ігнорування яких створює ризики репутаційних та фінансових втрат. Комплаєнс-контроль виявляє економічні та репутаційні ризики, здійснює профілактику та управління ними, формуючи комплекс реальних заходів із захисту бізнесу та його власників. Отже, впровадження системи комплаєнс-контролю є важливою складовою стратегії розвитку економічних суб'єктів, у тому числі готельного бізнесу, та актуальним об'єктом дослідження.

Мета і методи. Мета дослідження полягає у теоретичному аналізі комплаєнса готельного обслуговування та формуванні моделі, що визначає напрями удосконалення готельного обслуговування в умовах пандемічних ризиків. Компаративний характер комплаєнса як категорії доведення відповідності певним обмеженням сприяв застосуванню у процесі дослідження набору загальнонаукових методів, таких як абстрагування, аналіз та синтез, моделювання, елімінування факторів, які впливають на об'єкт дослідження, метод гепу для скорингу комплаєнса, що забезпечило системний характер дослідження та дозволило обґрунтувати запропоновані імперативи рамкових умов комплаєнса в готельному бізнесі.

Результати. Здійснено емпіричну оцінку фінансових втрат готелів від пандемії, спричиненої COVID-19 в Україні. Сформовано напрями комплаєнса готельного обслуговування. Скомпільовано імперативи рамкових умов обслуговування у готелях в умовах пандемії COVID-19. Здійснено скоринг комплаєнса готельного обслуговування методом гепу. **Висновки та обговорення.** Науково обґрунтовано, що концептуалізація комплаєнс-контролю готельного обслуговування є актуальним науковим завданням, оскільки дозволяє вивчити вимоги до нього і дотримуватися, що є необхідним у карантинних умовах. Подальші дослідження потребують поглиблення з огляду оцінки фінансових гепів впровадження імперативів рамкових умов у бізнес-процеси готелю, а також оцінювання нових форм готельного обслуговування, що сформувались у світовій практиці готельного бізнесу під час пандемії.

Ключові слова: комплаєнс-контроль, готельне обслуговування, COVID-19, метод гепу.

УДК 640.412:338.46]:616-036.21

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НАУЧНОЕ ОБОСНОВАНИЕ КОМПЛАЕНСА ГОСТИНИЧНОГО БИЗНЕСА В УСЛОВИЯХ ПАНДЕМИИ

Актуальность. Комплаенс-контроль как методология управления позволяет экономическому субъекту предотвращать репутационные и финансовые потери, а следовательно, обеспечить его эффективность. Поэтому внедрение системы комплаенс-контроля является важной составляющей стратегии развития гостиничного бизнеса и объектом исследования. Его актуальность заключается в определении основных аспектов комплаенс-контроля гостиничного обслуживания, основанных на нормативных и организационных положениях и процедурах, научно обоснованных концепциях. **Цель и методы.** Цель исследования заключается в теоретическом анализе комплаенса гостиничного обслуживания и определения направлений совершенствования стандартов гостиничного обслуживания в условиях пандемических рисков. Кроссдисциплинарная природа научной проблемы привела к применению в процессе исследования набора общенаучных методов, таких как абстрагирование, анализ и синтез, моделирование, элиминирование, что обеспечило системный характер исследования императивов комплаенса гостиничного обслуживания, его оценки. **Результаты.** Осуществлена эмпирическая оценка финансовых потерь отелей от пандемии, вызванной COVID-19 в Украине. Скомпилированы императивы рамочных условий обслуживания в гостиницах в условиях пандемии COVID-19. Осуществлен скоринг комплаенса гостиничного обслуживания методом гэта. **Выводы и обсуждение.** Исследование показало, что концептуализация комплаенс-контроля гостиничного обслуживания является актуальной научной задачей, поскольку позволяет изучить требования и научно обосновать новые стандарты, необходимые в карантинных условиях. Дальнейшие исследования требуют углубления, учитывая оценки финансовых гэпов внедрения императивов рамочных условий в бизнес-процессы отеля, а также оценки новых форм гостиничного обслуживания, сформировавшихся в мировой практике гостиничного бизнеса во время пандемии.

Ключевые слова: комплаенс-контроль, гостиничное обслуживание, COVID-19, метод гэта.